

Teaching public speaking

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Abstract. *In this article we have looked at a variety of techniques that can be used to help students develop the necessary skills for delivering public speeches. Practice in these areas can help to increase the students' overall confidence and fluency and provide an interesting and useful diversion from regular language work. This article contains activities that should help the students and lecturers develop public speaking skills. It should also help make students aware of the conventions of non-verbal communication.*

Keywords: *skills for delivering public speeches; language level; psychological barriers of public speaking; non-verbal communication (verbal); methodological recommendations; organizing teaching speaking.*

Обучение публичному говорению

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Аннотация. *В этой статье мы рассмотрели приёмы, необходимые студентам для формирования их умений публичного говорения. Постоянная практика в этой сфере поможет студентам повысить свой языковой уровень, преодолеть психологические барьеры выступления перед аудиторией, используя, в том числе, и невербальные формы коммуникации. Статья содержит и методические рекомендации для преподавателей по организации обучения говорению.*

Ключевые слова: *умение публичного говорения; языковой уровень; психологические барьеры выступления перед аудиторией; невербальные (вербальные); методические рекомендации; организация обучения говорению.*

Speaking is "the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts" [2, с. 13]. Speaking is considered to be the crucial part of second language learning and teaching. But despite its importance, for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as a repetition of drills or memorization of dialogues and oral topics. However, today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills, because, only in that way, students can express themselves and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative situation. In order to teach second language learners how to speak in the best way possible, some speaking activities are provided below, that can be applied to ESL and EFL auditoriums, together with suggestions for teachers who teach oral language.

Speaking in public is not something that most people enjoy, for many people, standing up in public and doing a speech is one of their greatest fears. For many language students in particular, this is the ultimate challenge. "What is public speaking? It involves talking in front of a group of people, with or without any preparation. It can be in front of people that you know (e.g. at a family celebration) or a crowd of strangers. It usually implies the interaction between the audience and the speaker – the speaker speaks, and the audience (hopefully) listens" [1, с.150].

Speeches have different functions. "These include being persuasive (e.g. trying to convince the audience to vote for you), informative (e.g. speaking about the dangers of climate change), entertaining (e.g. a best man's speech at a wedding) or celebratory (e.g. to introduce the winner of an award)" [8, с. 270]. Some speeches may

have more than one of these aims. Why is public speaking useful for our students?

All of us, at some points in our life, will need to stand up and speak in front of a group of people. Working on public speaking helps to develop overall fluency and requires considering how they speak as well as what they say. So, we must teach our students how to do this. "This is useful for speaking in any situation, public or otherwise. We must teach the students the necessary skills for doing this using such activities to promote speaking as discussions, role play, simulations, information gap, brainstorming, storytelling, interviews, story completion, reporting, picture narrating and picture describing" [3, с. 120].

Nowadays a presentation refers to a very important part of second language learning speaking in public and a common feature of working life in many companies. However, most of people have been already acquainted with this type of activity; but there are those who still do not know exactly how to make a good presentation. At our university we teach the students to follow definite effective steps.

First of all, the presentation must be thoroughly prepared and sketched out. Secondly, you should "keep your audience focused and interested. Giving an effective presentation means working with both the audience and the topic. It is important to know how to relate to who you are communicating with in order to get through to them. Think about the audience's point of view and what they have in common when planning a speech." [9, с. 148]. Actually it has three main parts including introduction, body and conclusion. Therefore, the talk should be clearly and logically structured so that the audience can understand it more easily. That is why the following phrases would be very helpful: *Greeting, name, position-* Good morning. My name's (...). I'm the new Finance

Manager. Ladies and gentlemen, it's an honour for me to have the opportunity to address such a distinguished audience. *Title/Subject-* I'd like to talk(to you) today about In my presentation I'd like to review... *.Reference to the audience-* I can see many of you are aware of ...*Setting the time-* My presentation will last for about five minutes. *Dealing with questions-*Please, stop me if you have any questions. *Outline/main parts-*I've divided my presentation into four parts/sections. They are ... *Introducing the first point-*To start with, then, I'd like to consider...*Finishing the point-*That's all I have to say about...*Starting a new point-* Now let's turn to...*Referring to what you have said-*As I said at the beginning... *Referring to what you will say-* I'll come to that later. *Rhetorical questions-*What's the explanation for this?

Any presentation is opened with title slide. In this respect we remind the students about the logo of the alma mater, the theme and the author. Then the outline comes. As far as, the presentation is designed in Powerpoint format you should not use many different colours with small font size and write too much information on one slide. There must not be ready sentences. Only phrases with nominative function (geographical names, dates, proper names) are allowed. The last thing is to make a list of questions you expect to be asked at the end of the presentation: " *That brings me to the end of my presentation. At this stage I'd like to go over/run through the main points I made. I'd be glad to try and answer any questions.* "

"As far as the first few minutes of a presentation are extremely important you should begin your talk by asking a rhetorical question, starting with an interesting fact or telling them a story or anecdote in order to create a relaxed atmosphere"[4, c. 281]. We pay special preference to different kinds of graphs and diagrams in the presentation and teach students to read and comment on them by means of authentic video material.

During the talk, you should highlight the information to help your audience to remember them via such techniques as: speaking about 20% more slowly than normal, stressing or using an auxiliary verb – *It is costing much money.*; do, does, did – *We do see a need for change*; changing the normal word order- *We are suggesting...* - *What we are suggesting...*; *I'm proposing...* - *What I'm proposing...*; or even making pauses in sentence if you feel necessary in order to emphasize the key points or express your enthusiasm.

Moreover, you must often make eye contact with each individual and spread attention around the audience while you are communicating with audience. "Particularly, the body language such as posture, gesture can help you interact with the audience better. During the talk, you should hold your body properly, keep your head up or keep hands by your side. You also should not scratch your hair or fiddle your jewellery. All of these actions are likely to distract the audience"[5, c. 213].

Recently organizing joint or group presentations has become very popular. It is connected with the necessity to present some joint projects in appropriate way. And here we teach our students not just to divide the presentation into two or three parts. It must be a pure interaction among the speakers! Each of them must be involved into the discussion. There must not be any outsiders!

You may reach it recommending your students to use rhetoric and disjunctive questions:

- What's the explanation for this?
- What can we do about it?
- How will this affect us?

Or:

-It is of great importance now, isn't it?
-It plays a great role in distributing the goods, doesn't it?

Or such phrases as:

- Now let's turn to...
- I'd like now to consider...
- Next we come to...
- The next point I'd like to make is...
- If I could now turn to...
- Now, turning to...
- Let me now turn to/move on to...
- As my colleague said at the beginning...
- My colleague told you a few minutes ago that...
- In the first part of our talk it was said...

"Unfortunately avoiding plagiarism is one more common problem. One way to tackle this is to ask the students not to write out their speeches in full but to use only notes or key words to help them deliver their speech. This then increases the chances of them being more original with the delivery"[7, c. 516]. Another option is to collect in the speeches and run whole sentences through an internet search engine to see if it comes up with anything. And of course, we should impress upon our students the importance of doing their own work!

While teaching oral language English language teachers should have look at a variety of techniques that can be used to help students develop the necessary skills for delivering public speeches. Practice in these areas can help to increase your students' overall confidence and fluency and provide an interesting and useful diversion from regular language work:

- You are to give maximum opportunity to students to speak the target language by providing a rich environment that contains collaborative work, authentic materials and tasks, and shared knowledge.

- It is our task to involve each student in every speaking activity; for this aim, practice different ways of student participation. Please, remember about teacher speaking time in class constantly increasing student speaking time. Step back and observe students.

-A good teacher indicates positive signs when commenting on a student's response.

- In order to prompt students to speak more ask eliciting questions such as "What do you mean? How did you reach that conclusion?"

- Your written feedback like "Your presentation was really great. It was a good job. I really appreciated your efforts in preparing the materials and efficient use of your voice..."will be the most relevant in the process of teaching foreign language.

- "Do not correct students' pronunciation mistakes very often while they are speaking. Correction should not distract student from his or her speech" [6,c.190].

- Involve speaking activities not only in class but also out of class; contact parents and other people who can help. Pay special attention to organizing extra-curricular activity.

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- Circulate around classroom to ensure that students are on the right track and see whether they need your help while they work in groups or pairs.

- Provide the vocabulary and necessary grammar structures beforehand that students need in speaking activities.

- Diagnose problems faced by students who have difficulty in expressing themselves in the target language and provide more opportunities to practice the spoken language.

So, teaching speaking is a very important part of second language learning. The ability to communicate in a second language clearly and efficiently contributes to the

success of the learner in school and success later in every phase of life. Therefore, it is essential that language teachers pay great attention to teaching speaking. Rather than leading students to pure memorization, providing a rich environment where meaningful communication takes place is desired. With this aim, various speaking activities such as those listed above can contribute a great deal to students in developing basic interactive skills necessary for life. These activities make students more active in the learning process and at the same time make their learning more meaningful and fun for them.

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